

ISic3108

I.Sicily inscription 3108

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Motya

Place of origin (modern)

Mozia

Provenance

Birgi necropolis

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mozia, Villa Whittaker, inventory 5422

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR105600

1. Φόλ

2. ος

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284792

EDR 105600

EDCS 65200114

Bibliography

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